

Uncatalysed and Copper(II)-catalysed Oxidative Decarboxylation of Acetic Acid. Kinetics and Mechanism

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Kinetics of the uncatalysed as well as the copper(II)-catalysed oxidative decarboxylation of acetic acid by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion have been investigated. In the uncatalysed oxidation the rate of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ decomposition is independent of acid concentration. In the copper(II)-catalysed reaction the exponents in the rate law

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k[S_2O_8^{2-}]^x [CH_3COO^-]^y [Cu^{II}]^z$$

are $x=0.8-2.0$, $y=0$, $z=0.2$. Probable mechanism elucidating the role of copper(II) is suggested.

THE peroxodisulphate ion has been extensively used as an oxidant¹. Despite the high oxidation potential for the half reaction,

the oxidation does not proceed at a conveniently measurable rate. Catalytic oxidation studies have, therefore, been mostly undertaken².

Of the various organic acids oxidised by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion, acetic acid oxidation remains the least investigated³. Herein, the results of the uncatalysed and Cu^{II} -catalysed oxidative decarboxylation of acetic acid by the peroxodisulphate ion are recorded.

Experimental

All chemicals were of E. Merck, G.R. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Reaction kinetics were followed by estimating peroxodisulphate iodometrically⁴.

In copper(II)-catalysed reaction, the $S_2O_8^{2-}$ equivalent to Cu^{II} concentration ($\geq 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) kept in any experiment in terms of titre volume (0.04 M) have been subtracted from the observed titre volume to obtain (a-x). For product analysis, the reaction mixture was kept at boiling water temperature under reflux for suitable time period. It was then distilled to separate the volatile and non-volatile fractions. Spot tests were carried out for identifying the products in these fractions.

Results and Discussion

Uncatalysed oxidation: The kinetics of the uncatalysed reaction were studied at 60° with different concentrations of the oxidant and the reductant.

From the linear plots of $\log(S_2O_8^{2-})$, vs time (Fig. 1), it is concluded that peroxodisulphate decomposition follows first order path in presence of

Fig. 1. First order linear plots at different $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$; $[CH_3COOH] = 0.02 \text{ M}$, temp. = 60°: (A) 0.01, (B) 0.02, (C) 0.04 and (D) 0.08 M.

acetic acid. The results of rate dependence on the concentrations of peroxodisulphate and acetic acid show that the first order rate constants decrease with the increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$. The log-log plot (Fig. 2) reveals 0.75 dependence in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$. The rate is independent of $[Acetic\ acid]_0$. However, at high concentrations of the acid, the first order rate constant decreases (Table 1).

Such kinetics point to the well established peroxodisulphate decomposition rate law in presence of a reductant.

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = [k_1 + k_2[X^\cdot][S_2O_8^{2-}]] \quad (1)$$

where, $[X^\cdot]$ is the concentration of the free radical produced from the reducing agent. The enhanced

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Fig. 2. Demonstration of 0.75 (slope) order in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ by log-log plot.

rate finds explanation from the value of the constant free radical concentration.

Product analysis as carried out in the volatile and non-volatile fractions indicate methanol, formaldehyde and formic acid with CO_2 (by chromotropic acid reaction spot test⁴). Evidently the hydrocarbons formed are further oxidised in minor amounts.

The proposed mechanism steps leading to the above rate expression could be,

where, $X^{\cdot}$ is the free radical $CO_3^{\cdot-}$, and P the products (also reported in the Ag^I -catalysed oxidation studies).

The disturbed first order peroxodisulphate decomposition and a relatively low value of the rate constant at high acid concentration indicate inhibition and free radical destruction by some reaction of an intermediate nature which causes fractional power dependence. As expected for a free radical reaction involving reducing species, such inhibitory features are exhibited⁶.

Cu^{II}-catalysed oxidation : In the Cu^{II} -catalysed oxidation, kinetic features of chain reaction are largely reproduced. However, the first order plots deviate from linearity at all concentrations of the reactants and the catalyst (Fig. 3). The dependence of rate was studied over a wide range of oxidant

Fig. 3. First order plots of Cu^{II} -catalysed oxidation of acetic acid by peroxodisulphate; $[AcA]=0.02 M$, $[Cu^{2+}]=1 \times 10^{-4} M$, temp. = 60° ; $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$: (A) 0.005, (B) 0.01, (C) 0.02, (D) 0.05 and (E) 0.10 M.

and catalyst (Table 2). Measurements to determine the exponents in the rate law,

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k[S_2O_8^{2-}]^x [CH_3COO^-]^y [Cu^{II}]^z \quad (2)$$

show that $x=0.8-2.0$, $y=0$ and $z=0.2$. The rate is found to be independent of $[Cu^{II}]_0$ at higher concentrations.

With progress of the reaction, pH decreases (Fig. 4) and the results indicate that the salt-effect depends more on the concentration and nature of the ion than on the ionic strength, since the rate increases differently using different salts. Free radical capture-agent (allyl acetate) is found to suppress the rate tremendously (cf. 8.06; 0.65). The effect of oxygen on the rate has been measured and as expected for a free radical reaction involving reducing species, oxygen inhibition is exhibited. Passage of nitrogen causes a rate increase presumably due to the removal of dissolved oxygen.

TABLE 1—RATE DEPENDENCE ON $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ AND $[CH_3COOH]_0$.

Temp. = 60°

$[CH_3COOH]_0 = 0.02 M$				$[K_2S_2O_8]_0 = 0.02 M$		
$[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ M	Rate $\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0^{-0.75}$ $\times 10^5$	k_1 $\times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$[OH_3COO^-]_0$ M	Rate $\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	k_1 $\times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.01	1.51	0.48	1.98	0.005	2.46	1.27
0.02	3.25	0.48	1.84	0.02	2.25	1.94
0.04	3.95	0.44	1.08	0.03	2.19	1.25
0.08	6.82	0.45	0.96	0.05	1.71	1.02

TABLE 2—RATE DEPENDENCE ON $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$, $[CH_3COO^-]_0$ AND $[Cu^{II}]_0$

Temp. = 60°

$[CH_3COOH]_0 = 0.02 M$ $[Cu^{II}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$				$[K_2S_2O_8]_0 = 0.02 M$ $[Cu^{II}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$		$[K_2S_2O_8]_0 = 0.02 M$ $[CH_3COOH]_0 = 0.02 M$			
$[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ M	Rate $\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0}$ $\times 10^5$	k_1 10^3 min^{-1}	$[CH_3COO^-]_0$ M	Rate $\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	$[Cu^{II}]_0$ $\times 10^4 M$	Rate $\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[Cu^{II}]_0}$ $\times 10^5$	k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.0010	0.076	0.60 ^a	0.88	0.010	8.55	0.10	5.00	0.50	8.45
0.0025	0.254	0.61 ^a	1.16	0.020	8.56	0.50	7.97	0.58	8.40
0.0050	0.610	0.60 ^a	1.87	0.030	8.58	1.00	8.56	0.54	8.06
0.010	1.98	19.80 ^b	2.58	0.040	8.67	2.00	9.21	0.51	9.21
0.015	4.67	20.75 ^b	5.95			4.00	11.51	—	18.05
0.020	8.56	21.40 ^b	8.06			6.00	11.54	—	12.50
0.030	13.98	0.23 ^c	8.19			10.00	11.37	—	12.79
0.050	20.60	0.23 ^c	6.87			20.00	11.54	—	18.82
0.080	31.92	0.28 ^c	4.99						
0.1000	34.46	0.22 ^c	8.95						

^a = 1.8, ^b 2.0 and ^c 0.8.Fig. 4. pH variation; $[AcA]_0 = [K_2S_2O_8]_0 = 0.02 M$, $[CuSO_4]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, temp. = 60°.

Mechanism: The kinetic characteristics reveal a striking similarity with those observed in other Cu^{II} -catalysed peroxodisulphate oxidation reactions⁷.

First, Cu^{II} in acetic acid exists as complex in solution.

Second, the catalysed reaction is faster by several orders of magnitude than the uncatalysed reaction.

Third, a mixture of Cu^{II} and acetic acid has a marked effect on peroxodisulphate decomposition. Neither of these alone appreciably effects the rate of peroxodisulphate decomposition.

Hence, the sequence,

is excluded on kinetic grounds⁷, whereas the bimolecular reaction,

To explain the results, it is proposed that the enhanced peroxodisulphate decomposition be

ascribed to the following reactions in addition to the sequences (i) to (iv),

It is likely that in the presence of the oxidising ions in the medium ($S_2O_8^{2-}$, $SO_4^{\cdot-}$, $OH^{\cdot}$) the Cu^{II} -complex oxidatively disproportionates to yield the products and Cu^{II} ions. In the process, the possibility of cupric ion being reduced is not ruled out. The cuprous ion is immediately oxidised to cupric ion and this is in conformity with the observations of Chaltykyan and Beilerian⁸ who found that peroxodisulphate does not oxidise the substrate in the presence of cuprous ion, instead the ion is immediately oxidised to cupric ion.

Thus peroxodisulphate decomposition occurs *via* pathways (i) and (iv), whereas step (vii) elucidates the catalytic role of Cu^{II} . This means that any single kinetic experiment obeys an integrated first order law, which shows that the rate of disappearance of peroxodisulphate is first order with respect to time. With respect to concentration, however, the reaction is second order at low values of peroxodisulphate and almost first order at higher values. At exceedingly low peroxodisulphate concentration the dependence could be between these two extremes. In a similar way, step (vii) implies the rate to be independent of acid as well as copper(II) concentrations, the cuprous ion immediately being oxidised to cupric ion, suggests a partial dependence in Cu^{II} at exceedingly low concentrations.

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